

Dextrose 5% in Water Injections for Pes Anserine Syndrome in Knee Osteoarthritis – A Case Series

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ABSTRACT

Background: Pes anserine syndrome is characterized by pain in the proximal medial tibial region, commonly associated with knee osteoarthritis (OA) due to its bursal sac inflammation. The usual course of treatment for pes anserine syndrome is supportive, ranging from physiotherapy to NSAIDs, with steroid injections for refractory cases. It was reported that the use of dextrose 5% in water (D5W) has shown promise in treating chronic musculoskeletal conditions without the adverse effects associated with steroids.

Objective: This study evaluates the efficacy of ultrasound-guided D5W and lidocaine injections in treating pes anserine syndrome in knee OA patients.

Study Design: This study is conducted towards three patients with pes anserine syndrome and knee OA.

Material and Methods: Three patients with pes anserine syndrome and knee OA received ultrasound-guided injections of a mixed 2cc D5W and 1cc lidocaine in a 3cc syringe guided by the ultrasound into the fascias between the pes anserine muscles. Pain was evaluated using the VAS five days later.

Results: All patients reported significant pain reduction of 25-75%, along with improvements in daily activities.

Discussion: The role of D5W injections in pain relief is presumably linked with various mechanisms. In this study, lidocaine provided immediate pain relief, while D5W sustained its effects by stabilizing neural activity, normalizing regional glucose metabolism, and reducing neurogenic inflammation.

Conclusion: D5W injections proved a promising result to replace steroids in treating pes anserine syndrome, although further studies are needed to confirm efficacy and optimize treatment protocols.

KEYWORDS: Pes anserine syndrome, D5W injection, knee osteoarthritis

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INTRODUCTION

Knee osteoarthritis is a common arthritic syndrome, usually caused by degenerative processes. The prevalence rate ranges between 10% and 12% in the general population. It is one of the most frequent explanations for pain, limits on activities, and participation restrictions. When it comes to activity limitation and impairment in knee osteoarthritis, pain is the main symptom and most likely the most significant component. Three muscle tendons (the sartorius, gracilis, and semitendinosus) that attach at the proximal medial tibia make

up the pes anserine. These tendons help maintain the "cross-legged" stance by supporting internal tibial rotation, flexor flexion, and protection against rotatory and valgus stress on the knee.^{1,2}

A clinical condition known as pes anserine syndrome is linked to pain in the proximal medial tibial region and the medial knee. The bursal sac may or may not become inflamed. Activities that are repeated may make the symptoms worse. Pes anserine syndrome is associated with

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risk factors such as female gender, obesity, and osteoarthritis.²

The usual course of treatment for pes anserine syndrome is supportive. Typically, it consists of physiotherapy and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medications (NSAIDs). Injection of steroid may be needed for refractory cases.^{1,2} Dextrose 5% in water (D5W) has demonstrated its efficacy comparable to that of steroid in treating chronic rotator cuff tendinopathy and ulnar neuropathy. D5W in the long-term are more effective than steroid which may be superior in showing the short-term effects. D5W also more effective than triamcinolone in carpal tunnel study at 4-6 months. Nowadays, many clinical researchers have illustrated that US-guided D5W injections into the carpal tunnel have similar efficacy as steroids for improving pain intensity, functional limitation in daily life, electrophysiological parameters, and US outcomes. Systematic review and meta-analysis have shown that the US-guided perineural injection of D5W way more effective compared to steroid in treatment of carpal tunnel syndrome. The D5W injections can be safely administered to patients with diabetes without the risk of increasing blood glucose levels due to its low total amount of glucose, injected locally, and does not enter blood flow.³

Goals of regional D5W injections are to modulate referred pain and support tissue repair, by administering injections into dysfunctional soft tissues such as muscles and ligaments or also can be injected into joint cavities, around peripheral nerves, or into epidural space.^{3,4}

This case series presents an US-guided pes anserine fascia hydrodissection using D5W and lidocaine with an interesting risk-benefit ratio. We present three clinical cases in which D5W and lidocaine was used for treatment of pes anserine syndrome in knee osteoarthritis. Hopefully, steroid injections can be replaced with D5W in daily medical practice in the future.

CASE PRESENTATION

Methods

Three patients who presented with pes anserine syndrome and knee osteoarthritis were treated by hydrodissection injection of a mixed 2cc D5W and 1cc lidocaine in a 3cc syringe guided by the ultrasound into the fascias between the pes anserine muscles.

The follow up session was recorded on the fifth day after the injection. The main parameters recorded is pain scale using VAS.

RESULTS

Case 1

A 55-year-old woman diagnosed with grade 2 knee OA presented to the clinic on December 2023 with knee pain on her medial right knee, worsened by sit to stand and activity on the stairs. She had taken NSAIDS as her oral analgesia but

never had physical therapy previously. Her pain scale was NRS 8 in the first meeting. Then physical examination found that she was obese 1 with BMI of 26.67kg/m², bilateral knee valgum deformity, and tenderness on her pes anserine. USG showed a thickened pes anserinus tendon insertion without fluid accumulation. Per our methods, the patient received 2mL of D5W and 1mL of lidocaine 2% injected into the fascias of the pes anserinus.

After the injection, the patient was re-evaluated and noted a 50% pain improvement with NRS 4. Then the patient was re-evaluated in 5 days. The patient still reported 4/10 pain scale on the fifth day and improvement in her overall daily activities.

Case 2

A 53-year-old woman diagnosed with grade 2 knee OA presented to the clinic on December 2023 with knee pain on her medial left knee, worsened by sit to stand and walking long distance. She had taken NSAIDS and received hyaluronic acid into her intraarticular of the knee, but never had physical therapy previously. Her pain scale was NRS 7 in the first meeting. From the physical examination was found that she was overweight with BMI of 24.4kg/m², bilateral knee valgum deformity, and tenderness on her pes anserine. USG showed a thickened pes anserinus tendon insertion without fluid accumulation. Per our methods, the patient received 2mL of D5W and 1mL of lidocaine 2% injected into the fascias of the pes anserinus.

After the injection, the patient was re-evaluated and noted an approximately 25% pain improvement with NRS 5. Then the patient was re-evaluated in 5 days. The patient then reported 3/10 pain scale on the fifth day and improvement in her overall daily activities.

Case 3

A 49-years-old woman diagnosed with grade 2 knee OA presented to the clinic on February 2024 with knee pain on her medial both knees, worsened by stairs climbing and sit to stand. She had taken NSAIDS and received hyaluronic acid into her intraarticular of the knee, but never had physical therapy previously. Her pain scale was NRS 8 on the left knee and 7 on the right knee in the first meeting. From the physical examination was found that she was overweight with BMI of 25.1kg/m², bilateral knee valgum deformity, and tenderness on her pes anserine. USG showed a thickened pes anserinus tendon insertion with minimal fluid accumulation in her pes anserine bursae. Per our methods, the patient received 2mL of D5W and 1mL of lidocaine 2% injected into the fascias of the pes anserinus.

After the injection, the patient was re-evaluated and noted an approximately 75% pain improvement with NRS 2-3. Then the patient was re-evaluated in 5 days. The patient then reported 4/10 pain scale on the fifth day and improvement in her overall daily activities.

DISCUSSION

The connective tissue known as fascia forms a continuous matrix of structural support that spans the whole body. It surrounds and penetrates blood vessels, muscles, bones, and nerves. Since the fascia is the source of many muscle fibers, myofascial insertions form sequences by extending longitudinally between several synergic muscle groups. Acute inflammation or tissue damage can lead to the formation of adhesions, which can cause pain as the fascia becomes more rigid and less pliable.⁵ Muscular action is coordinated by the muscle fascia, which is extensively innervated with free and encapsulated nerve terminals that may transmit nociceptive signals. Hyaluronic acid is the most concentrated in the fascia's layer of the loose connective tissue, according to Stecco et al. Large volumes of hyaluronic acid are created in response to overuse or injury to the muscles. These molecules aggregate into a supermolecular structure, increasing viscosity and reducing the fascia's ability to slide, which causes friction. The nociceptors and mechanoreceptors in the fascia are irritated by the friction. Fascial mobility is linked to myofascial pain and can be reduced by a number of other conditions, including ischemia, acidosis, muscular hyperexcitability, peripheral sensitization, and chronic inflammation.⁵

Interfascial block is one of the few methods for relieving myofascial pain. Kobayashi et al. state that these followings are potential mechanisms of pain relief in an interfascial block: (1) sodium channel block by a local anesthetic; (2) acid stimuli by injection of low pH solution; (3) puncture stimuli by needle injection; (4) mechanical stimuli to the myofascial by injection of a solution; (5) washout of various algesic substances in the interfascial space; (6) separation of the myofascial layers, which lowers muscular friction and increases fascial mobility. Injections into the interfascia improve function and discomfort.⁶

Regional D5W injections have gained popularity in the past twenty years for the treatment of neuropathic and musculoskeletal pain.³ USG is a convenient, affordable, safe, and good way to visualize MSK architecture during musculoskeletal (MSK) intervention.⁷

There are three theoretical mechanisms presumed of how dextrose improves pain. First, an ion channel known as a major pain modulator may be impacted by dextrose. When it comes to the development of allodynia and hyperalgesia in chronic pain patients, the transient receptor potential vanilloid receptor-1 (TRPV1) ion channel is crucial. Second, in the setting of persistent pain, dextrose may refill low energy storage. Peripheral nerves are especially vulnerable to glycopenia, and even a 25% reduction in systemic dextrose over time might cause histopathologic damage to them. Perineural glycopenia causes nociceptive nerve fibers to become increasingly depolarized and hyperexcitable, most likely as a result of the ATPase pump's decreased efficiency. The ATPase pump is dependent on dextrose to produce ATP. Injections of dextrose have the potential to alleviate pain by

rectifying localized glycopenia. Third, co-administration of D5W has been shown to have a hyperpolarization impact on the neurons, reducing discomfort associated with the infusion of several chemotherapeutic drugs.⁸

In this case series, the pain was relieved shortly after the patients were injected. It may also be due to the effect of lidocaine which has the onset of action within 1,5 minutes and duration of action of 30 minutes to 3 hours locally.⁹ Pain relief which persisted until the 5th day is more likely due to the hydrodissection and the effects of D5W which include stabilization of neural activity, normalization of regional glucose metabolism, and decreased neurogenic inflammation. Further studies are important to explore the effect of D5W injection in term of MSK pain management.

CONCLUSION

Pes anserine syndrome is a medical condition that causes pain in the medial knee, which may or may not be accompanied with bursal sac inflammation. The patients in this clinical case series were given an injection of mixed D5W and lidocaine for hydrodissection. Following the injection, the patients experienced reduced pain that lasted for five days. To determine whether this strategy—which uses less steroids—can be used as a possible treatment for people with pes anserinus syndrome, more clinical study is needed.

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